

Brief Note

Fruit-Derived Biostimulants Promote *In Vitro* Regeneration in Mature Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) Embryos

Joseph Diaz^{1*}, Rich Milton Dulay^{2,3}, Sofronio Kalaw^{2,3}, Mary Jhane Valentino^{2,4}

Abstract

Several fruits in the Philippines are widely consumed for their delicious taste and health-promoting potential; however, some are discarded due to their unappealing taste, especially when overripe. The Saba banana (*Musa acuminata* var. *Balbiensis* L.) and mature coconut water (*Cocos nucifera* L.) are two of the most discarded fruits in the Philippines when over-ripe. Thus, to further utilise these products, their morphophysiological effects on the growth of mature Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) embryos *in vitro* were assessed for their potential use as an alternative biostimulant during micropropagation. The study revealed that *in-vitro* growth of mature calamansi embryos was enhanced by the fruit extracts, even in the absence of synthetic hormone, 6-BAP, as shown by improvements in plant height, growth rate, shoot and root length, leaf size and leaf area, stomatal features such as density and aperture, chlorophyll content, and water retention percentage. These findings suggest that these commonly discarded fruits may serve as effective biostimulants and a cheaper alternative to synthetic hormones for plant tissue culture, particularly for calamansi micropropagation. This work supports the potential of agricultural by-products in advancing sustainable plant propagation practices.

Keywords

Micropropagation; morpho-physiology; calamansi embryo; discarded fruits; 6-benzyl-aminopurine

1 Department of Biology, College of Natural Sciences, Benguet State University, La Trinidad, Benguet, Philippines

2 Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

3 Center for Tropical Mushroom Research and Development, Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

4 Biotechnology and Analytical Laboratory, Department of Biological Sciences, College of Science, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: j.diaz@bsu.edu.ph

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Uporaba izbranih pogosto zavrženih filipinskih sadežev kot naravni biostimulant za *in vitro* regeneracijo zrelih zarodkov kalamansija (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge)

Izvleček

Na Filipinih je, zaradi svojega okusnega okusa in zdravju koristnih lastnosti, razširjeno uživanje številnih vrst sadja. Kljub temu se nekateri plodovi, zlasti ko so prezreli, zavržejo zaradi neprivačnega okusa. Banana saba (*Musa acuminata* var. *balbiensis* L.) in voda zrelega kokosa (*Cocos nucifera* L.) sta med najbolj pogosto zavrženima sadežema na Filipinih, ko prezorita. Zato so bili za nadaljnjo uporabo teh proizvodov ocenjeni njihovi morfološko-fiziološki učinki na rast zrelega zarodka kalamansija (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) *in vitro*, z namenom raziskati njihovo morebitno uporabo kot alternativni biostimulant med mikropropagacijo. Raziskava je pokazala, da je bila *in vitro* rast zrelih zarodkov kalamansija izboljšana z izvlečki sadja, tudi v odsotnosti sintetičnega hormona 6-BAP, kar se je pokazalo v izboljšanju višine rastline, hitrosti rasti, dolžine poganjkov in korenin, velikosti listov in listne površine, lastnosti listnih rež, kot so gostota in odprtost, vsebnosti klorofila ter odstotka zadrževanja vode. Ti rezultati nakazujejo, da lahko pogosto zavrženo sadje služi kot učinkovit biostimulant in cenejša alternativa sintetičnim hormonom za tkivno kulturo rastlin, zlasti pri mikropropagaciji kalamansija. Delo podpira potencial kmetijskih stranskih proizvodov pri spodbujanju trajnostnih praks razmnoževanja rastlin.

Ključne besede

mikropropagacija; morfofiziologija; kalamansi zarodek; zavrženo sadje; 6-benzyl-aminopurine

Introduction

Global population growth and climate change continue to intensify abiotic stresses that limit crop productivity and threaten food security (Wallace et al., 2003; Parry, 2019). While conventional agricultural intensification has improved yields, it has also caused significant environmental degradation, prompting the search for sustainable and low-impact alternatives (Tilman et al., 2002; Foley et al., 2011). Among these, plant tissue culture has emerged as an effective strategy for the rapid propagation of uniform, disease-free planting materials, particularly for perennial horticultural crops.

Successful *in vitro* regeneration depends on the interaction between explant type, basal culture medium, and growth-regulating substances. Synthetic plant growth regulators (PGRs) are widely used to control morphogenesis; however, their high cost and environmental burden have stimulated interest in natural, plant-derived biostimulants (Bradford & Trewavas, 1994; Santner & Estelle, 2009). Fruit extracts, plant-derived liquids, and seaweed-based products contain endogenous phytohormones, vitamins, amino acids, and sugars that can promote cell division and differentiation *in vitro* (Hamdeni et al., 2022; Dumale et al., 2016; Azzam et al., 2022).

On the other hand, banana pulp and coconut water have been extensively used in plant tissue culture as organic supplements to enhance growth and regeneration. Nevertheless, most previous studies have incorporated these materials as additives to complex basal media or in combination with synthetic PGRs, limiting understanding of their independent biostimulant effects, particularly in citrus species (Bautista and Valentino 2023). Moreover, few studies have explored the use of locally discarded fruit materials as primary growth-promoting agents within simplified culture systems.

In the Philippines, overripe Saba banana (*Musa acuminata* var. *balbisiana*) and mature coconut water (*Cocos nucifera* L.) are commonly discarded in public markets despite their documented biochemical and biological potential (Tecson-Mendoza, 2007; Sidhu & Zafar, 2018; Diaz et al., 2025a). Their valorisation as natural biostimulants offers an opportunity to integrate sustainable waste utilisation with plant propagation technologies, contributing to circular bioeconomy approaches (Pontillas et al., 2025)

Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) is a native and economically important citrus crop in the Philippines, valued for its culinary and industrial applications. However, its production has declined in recent years due to reduced planting areas, pest pressure, and climatic stress (PSA,

2017; PSA, 2023). In vitro propagation provides a promising means to support calamansi production by enabling rapid multiplication of high-quality planting materials. And recently, Diaz et al. (2025b) explored the use of exopolysaccharides from mushrooms as a biostimulant for Calamansi embryo culture in vitro.

Moreover, mature embryos were used as explants since they are developmentally stable, exhibit high regenerative potential, and reduce somaclonal variation compared with callus or vegetative tissues. Embryo culture also bypasses prolonged juvenile phases commonly encountered in citrus micropropagation and minimises contamination associated with field-derived explants (Miguel and Marum 2011; Catalano et al., 2022). Knudson C medium was selected as the basal medium due to its relatively simple nutrient composition, which allows clearer evaluation of biostimulant effects without interference from high salt concentrations or complex hormonal interactions characteristic of more commonly used media such as Murashige and Skoog (Hossain et al., 2010; Pradhan et al., 2016; Nongdam et al., 2023).

Hence, this study was to evaluate the effects of selected commonly discarded Philippine fruits as natural biostimulants on the in vitro regeneration of mature calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa* Bunge) embryos. It was hypothesised that fruit-derived extracts would enhance morphophysiological growth responses and could serve as cost-effective, sustainable alternatives to synthetic plant growth regulators in citrus micropropagation systems.

Materials and Methods

Plant Material and Sterilisation

Calamansi (*Citrus microcarpa*) seeds were obtained from a fresh, healthy Calamansi fruit. The seeds were then washed thoroughly with soap and running water and air-dried overnight. Once the seed coats became dry, they were manually removed and underwent further sterilisation. Seed sterilisation was done under a laminar airflow environment. The seeds were soaked in 5% NaOCl for 3-5 minutes, in bactericide for 10 minutes, 80% ethanol for 1 minute and 5 ppm plant preservation solution (PPS) for 15 minutes; and the seeds were rinsed with sterile distilled water three times after soaking. When fully sterilised, seeds were placed in a sterile petri plate with filter paper

for further drying, and 3 embryos from each seed were excised carefully and transferred to another petri plate with filter paper prior to inoculation.

Preparation of Tissue Culture Media

Knudson C Basal Media was used as basal medium for the mature Calamansi embryos. Over-ripe Saba banana extract and mature coconut water were supplemented on the Knudson C basal media at 2.5%, 5%, 7.5% and 10% concentration with and without 6-benzylaminopurine (6-BAP) at 1 ppm. Before autoclaving, the pH of the prepared media was adjusted to 5.7, and approximately 20 mL of the prepared media was poured into individual tissue culture bottles and sterilised (121°C, 15 psi) for 30 minutes.

Inoculation, Incubation and Morphophysiological Characterisation

Mature Calamansi embryos were inoculated aseptically on the previously sterilised tissue culture media with ten biological replicates (independent mature embryos) per treatment. After inoculation, the cultures were maintained in a plant growth chamber set at 25°C temperature, 40% humidity, and with a photoperiod of 16 hours light and 8 hours dark using cool white, fluorescent lamps at an intensity of approximately 60 mol m⁻² s⁻¹. After 21 days, the morphological characteristics such as shoots, roots and leaves were assessed along with the growth rate, fresh and dry weight. In addition, physiological parameters such as chlorophyll content, stomatal analysis and water loss percentage were recorded (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Plant Growth Rate (Height Increment)

Plant height was measured and calculated using a vernier calliper. The shoot length and root length of the plantlets were measured after 21 days, as well as the total length from the tip of the roots to the tip of the leaves. The average growth rate was computed by the total plant length divided by total incubation days (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Leaf Characterization

The leaf characters were evaluated after 21 days. The longest leaf length and width per treatment were measured using a vernier calliper. In computing the leaf size, the

length of the leaf is multiplied by its width (Schrader et al., 2021). The leaf area is computed by π (3.14) divided by 4 multiplied by the leaf length and leaf width (Shabani et al., 2016).

Chlorophyll Content Quantification

The fresh leaves of the plantlets were weighed, ground using a mortar and pestle with 3 mL of 80% acetone, and transferred to a conical tube. Chlorophyll extracts were collected and adjusted to 10 mL and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The derived supernatant was analysed for the total amount (mg/g) of chlorophyll estimation using a spectrophotometer at absorbances 645 and 663 nm. The obtained values were substituted in the formulas for the estimation of photosynthetic pigments (Lichtenthaler, 1987).

Water Loss Percentage

The total fresh weight from each treatment was measured using an analytical balance. To determine the oven-dry weight, the samples were placed in a drying oven at 40°C. The dry weight was recorded when the samples were at constant weight after several weighings. The percentage weight loss was calculated by subtracting the fresh and dry weight from the fresh weight multiplied by 100 (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Stomatal Analysis

The leaves from the plantlet were used by imprinting the stomata from the abaxial surface of the leaf using a thin layer of nail polish. Once dried, a piece of clear adhesive tape was pressed onto the nail-polished area, carefully removed, and mounted onto a glass slide. It was then viewed under a microscope at 400x magnification, and images were captured and processed using ImageJ software by obtaining the stomatal length, width, and aperture. Additionally, the stomatal density was obtained by calculating the number of stomata over the area of the field view (Diaz et al., 2025b).

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as mean \pm SD, with ten biological replicates (independent mature embryos) per treatment. The experiment followed a completely randomised design

(CRD). Differences among treatments were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and mean values were compared using Dunnett's post-hoc test with Knudson C medium supplemented with 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP) as the positive control, using RStudio software. Data normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test, and homogeneity of variances was evaluated using Levene's test. When assumptions of ANOVA were not met, data were transformed or analysed using the Kruskal–Wallis test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Plant Height and Growth Rate

As shown in Table 1, all treatments supplemented with Saba banana or mature coconut water extracts produced significantly greater plant height and growth rate compared to the control medium (Knudson C with 6-BAP). The control without 6-BAP exhibited minimal growth (3.30 mm plant height and 0.16 mm/day growth rate), highlighting the importance of organic supplementation for plant development. While treatments at 7.5% concentration showed numerically higher plant height, these values were not significantly different from the control beyond the overall treatment effect. The addition of 6-BAP did not consistently improve growth, as some treatments without 6-BAP showed comparable responses to the control.

Shoot and Root Length

Calamansi mature embryos grown in biostimulant-supplemented media, as shown in Table 1, exhibited greater shoot and root lengths compared to the control without 6-BAP (1.16 mm shoot length and 1.28 mm root length). Embryos cultured in mature coconut water (7.5–10%) without 6-BAP and in Saba banana extract (7.5%) without 6-BAP produced longer shoots than the control; however, these increases were not statistically significant beyond the overall treatment effect. Root length was also improved in organic extract treatments, with Saba banana extract (7.5%) without 6-BAP producing longer roots than the control, while coconut water treatments showed moderate increases. Overall, all organic extract treatments significantly improved shoot and root development compared to the control, which produced the shortest roots and shoots.

Tabela 1. Plant height, growth rate, shoot and root length of *in vitro* grown mature Calamansi Embryo in Knudson C with different fruit concentrations.Table 1. Višina rastline, hitrost rasti, dolžina poganjkov in korenin *in vitro* gojenega zrelega zarodka kalamansija v Knudson C z različnimi koncentracijami sadja.

Treatments	Plant Height (mm)	Growth Rate (mm/day)	Shoot (mm)	Root (mm)
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	40.29±10.98a	1.91±0.52a	21.14±5.62a	19.15±8.27a
Saba Banana (5%) w/o 6-BAP	46.48±15.49a	2.21±0.73a	24.83±13.61a	21.65±2.98a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	59.51±2.62a	2.83±0.12a	35.50±2.67a	24.01±0.95a
Saba Banana (10%) w/o 6-BAP	47.22±6.73a	2.24±0.32a	24.04±3.23a	22.42±4.05a
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	25.93±8.42b	1.23±0.40a	18.55±2.77a	7.37±6.12a
Saba Banana (5%) w/ 6-BAP	34.87±5.58a	1.66±0.26a	23.15±2.83a	11.71±4.20a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	36.19±8.52a	1.72±0.40a	21.68±5.49a	14.51±7.14a
Saba Banana (10%) w/ 6-BAP	31.48±9.85a	1.49±0.68a	21.35±9.59a	10.12±6.17a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	31.93±5.38a	1.52±0.25a	22.24±8.20a	9.36±5.64a
Coconut Water (5%) w/o 6-BAP	42.53±9.43a	2.02±0.44a	27.61±16.73a	10.81±3.39a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	46.81±1.47a	2.22±0.07a	38.67±16.73a	14.27±8.46a
Coconut Water (10%) w/o 6-BAP	41.89±24.07a	1.99±1.14a	37.75±3.14a	9.05±1.67a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	31.43±16.69a	1.49±0.79a	22.57±6.63a	8.86±10.06a
Coconut Water (5%) w/ 6-BAP	33.87±8.90a	1.61±0.42a	25.25±5.83a	8.61±4.28a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	30.52±7.78a	1.45±0.37a	22.60±5.46a	7.91±2.97a
Coconut Water (10%) w/ 6-BAP	27.91±8.42a	1.32±0.40a	19.55±7.83a	8.36±0.61a
Knudson C w/o 6-BAP	3.30±0.60b	0.16±0.02b	1.16±0.83b	1.28±0.18b
Knudson C w/ 6-BAP	30.47±6.47a	1.45±0.30a	22.78±4.51a	7.52±2.25a

Values are expressed as mean ± SD. Means with the same letter superscripts are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using Dunnett's Test (Knudson C w/ 6-BAP).

Tabela 2. Leaf characters, total chlorophyll content and percentage water loss of *in vitro* grown mature Calamansi embryo in Knudson C with different fruit concentrations.Table 2. Listne značilnosti, skupna vsebnost klorofila in odstotek izgube vode *in vitro* gojenega zrelega zarodka kalamansija v Knudson C z različnimi koncentracijami sadja.

Treatments	Leaf Size (mm)	Leaf Area (mm ²)	Total Chlorophyll Content (mg/g)	Water Loss (%)
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	13.20±8.41 ^b	10.36±6.60 ^b	5.19±1.63 ^b	70.14±0.40 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/o 6-BAP	19.63±15.14 ^b	15.41±11.88 ^b	6.49±2.14 ^b	80.45±8.82 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	60.38±14.27 ^a	47.40±11.20 ^a	27.81±0.94 ^a	75.21±11.71 ^a
Saba Banana (10%) w/o 6-BAP	19.62±0.81 ^a	15.40±0.63 ^b	13.71±5.67 ^b	72.46±7.82 ^a
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	15.24±6.80 ^b	12.47±2.68 ^b	5.53±1.93 ^b	77.57±0.52 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/ 6-BAP	46.14±29.71 ^a	12.63±4.68 ^b	4.64±1.04 ^b	78.98±8.33 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	62.20±43.76 ^a	12.68±4.07 ^b	4.26±0.60 ^b	72.40±8.17 ^a
Saba Banana (10%) w/ 6-BAP	19.30±11.61 ^a	15.15±0.63 ^b	4.07±0.74 ^b	65.32±8.92 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	8.03±5.81 ^b	6.30±4.56 ^b	4.54±1.27 ^b	77.42±6.97 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/o 6-BAP	18.78±8.17 ^b	14.74±6.41 ^b	4.81±1.36 ^b	79.56±8.51 ^a

Coconut Water (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	52.32±59.65 ^a	41.07±46.83 ^a	12.24±3.28 ^b	82.24±7.67 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/o 6-BAP	78.98±3.96 ^a	62.01±3.11 ^a	34.74±7.2 ^a	67.26±9.22 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	21.87±20.04 ^a	23.30±13.50 ^a	10.22±3.09 ^b	82.40±7.67 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/ 6-BAP	77.86±58.61 ^a	20.35±13.62 ^a	16.90±5.59 ^b	82.88±3.44 ^a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	103.32±9.58 ^a	20.56±13.75 ^a	14.09±2.68 ^b	71.95±4.55 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/ 6-BAP	23.23±17.43 ^a	18.23±13.68 ^a	12.98±7.85 ^b	59.31±10.32 ^a
Knudson C w/o 6-BAP	0.61±0.16 ^b	0.47±0.13 ^b	9.05±4.95 ^b	71.09±5.67 ^a
Knudson C w/ 6-BAP	36.32±9.70 ^a	28.5±10.39 ^a	39.73±3.91 ^a	69.60±10.43 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SD. Means with the same letter superscripts are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using Dunnett's Test (Knudson C w/ 6 BAP).

Leaf Characters and Chlorophyll Content

For leaf characteristics (Table 2), treatments supplemented with coconut water (7.5–10%), with or without 6-BAP, produced larger leaves than the control without fruit extract, which had the smallest leaves (0.61 mm length and 0.47 mm² area). Saba banana treatments also resulted in greater leaf size than the control. Although numerical differences were observed among the organic treatments, all treatments produced significantly larger leaves compared to the control.

Total chlorophyll content (Table 2) was higher in organic extract treatments than in the control without 6-BAP (9.05 mg/g). Coconut water at 10% without 6-BAP and Saba banana at 7.5% without 6-BAP showed higher chlorophyll values than the control. Some treatments with 6-BAP had lower chlorophyll levels; however, differences among treatments were not statistically significant except in comparison with the control.

Water Content Loss

Water loss (Table 2) varied across treatments, but differences among treatments were not statistically significant except when compared with the control (71.09% without 6-BAP; 69.60% with 6-BAP). Some treatments exhibited higher or lower water loss than the control, indicating that fruit extract supplementation influenced water retention, although the overall treatment effects were comparable to the control.

Stomatal Characteristics

Stomatal traits (length, width, density, and aperture) shown in Table 3 generally did not differ significantly from the control. However, stomatal density was significantly lower in the control without 6-BAP (117.97/mm²) compared with the organic extract treatments. Other stomatal measurements varied slightly among treatments but remained statistically comparable to the control. Overall, organic supplementation produced stomatal characteristics similar to or slightly improved relative to the control without 6-BAP.

Tabela 3. Stomatal characteristics of *in vitro* grown mature Calamansi Embryo in Knudson C with different fruit concentrations.

Table 3. Stomatne značilnosti *in vitro* gojenega zrelega zarodka kalamansija v Knudson C z različnimi koncentracijami sadja.

Treatments	Length (µm)	Width (µm)	Density (per mm ²)	Aperture (µm)
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.06±0.36 ^a	5.03±0.25 ^a	182.38±33.27 ^a	0.97±0.12 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.10±0.71 ^a	5.73±0.85 ^a	186.58±13.09 ^a	0.99±0.14 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.27±0.61 ^a	5.23±0.64 ^a	194.96±45.35 ^a	1.01±0.07 ^a
Saba Banana (10%) w/o 6-BAP	5.02±0.20 ^a	4.94±0.46 ^a	199.16±25.41 ^a	1.08±0.13 ^a
Saba Banana (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.2±0.44 ^a	4.83±0.14 ^a	205.45±25.41 ^a	0.89±0.22 ^a
Saba Banana (5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.31±0.30 ^a	5.02±0.26 ^a	201.25±6.28 ^a	1.01±0.15 ^a
Saba Banana (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.33±0.47 ^a	4.96±0.23 ^a	192.87±15.82 ^a	0.84±0.04 ^a

Saba Banana (10%) w/ 6-BAP	6.74±0.89 ^a	4.92±0.11 ^a	186.58±7.26 ^a	0.82±0.13 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/o 6-BAP	4.66±0.41 ^a	4.85±0.13 ^a	194.96±10.89 ^a	1.26±0.18 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.13±0.42 ^a	5.02±0.26 ^a	208.65±17.23 ^a	1.09±0.32 ^a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/o 6-BAP	5.36±0.43 ^a	5.07±0.17 ^a	178.19±19.21 ^a	1.03±0.16 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/o 6-BAP	5.62±0.34 ^a	4.92±0.52 ^a	174.00±62.04 ^a	0.92±0.14 ^a
Coconut Water (2.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.11±0.10 ^a	5.73±0.85 ^a	182.38±22.67 ^a	0.98±0.11 ^a
Coconut Water (5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.27±0.13 ^a	5.23±0.64 ^a	188.67±33.27 ^a	1.13±0.15 ^a
Coconut Water (7.5%) w/ 6-BAP	5.15±0.21 ^a	5.09±0.27 ^a	190.77±15.82 ^a	0.95±0.05 ^a
Coconut Water (10%) w/ 6-BAP	5.10±0.89 ^a	4.81±0.51 ^a	209.64±62.99 ^a	0.86±0.14 ^a
Knudson C w/o 6-BAP	4.46±0.52 ^a	3.62±0.90 ^b	117.97±15.97 ^b	0.87±0.09 ^a
Knudson C w/ 6-BAP	5.26±0.35 ^a	4.81±0.23 ^a	192.87±42.81 ^a	0.94±0.13 ^a

Values are expressed as mean ± SD. Means with the same letter superscripts are not significantly different at 5% level of significance using Dunnett's Test (Knudson C w/ 6-BAP).

Discussion

Plant tissue culture depends on nutrients, hormones, organic compounds, and environmental factors (Pasternak & Steinmacher, 2024). Various basal media have been developed, including Knudson C (Knudson et al., 1946), Vacin and Went (Vacin & Went, 1949), Hyponex (Kano, 1965), and Murashige and Skoog (Murashige & Skoog, 1962), with Murashige and Skoog being widely used for many plant species (Kumara et al., 2022). Despite their effectiveness, the high costs of basal media components necessitate exploring affordable alternatives. In this study, Knudson C medium was supplemented with fruit wastes, such as Saba banana and mature coconut water, to evaluate their effects on the *in vitro* growth of mature calamansi embryos.

On the other hand, shoot and root length are critical indicators of morphogenesis and plantlet vigour. Shoot elongation reflects proper shoot initiation, while root length ensures efficient nutrient uptake and acclimatisation (Rokosa & Kulpa, 2019). The results showed that 6-BAP enhanced shoot length in some cases, but lower to moderate concentrations of fruit extracts without 6-BAP often promoted better root elongation, particularly with Saba banana. Coconut water favoured shoot growth more than root elongation, likely due to its cytokinin content (Ge et al., 2005). Treatments without organic supplementation, especially Knudson C without 6-BAP, resulted in the poorest growth, emphasising the importance of fruit-derived additives in supplying vitamins, sugars, amino acids, and natural plant growth regulators (Mok & Mok, 2001; Ge et al., 2005; David et al., 2015; Lazim et al., 2015; Gansau et al., 2016;

Mardhikari et al., 2020). High cytokinin levels from 6-BAP sometimes inhibited root growth, consistent with previous reports (Auer, 1996; Laplaze et al., 2007; Thorpe, 2008).

Moreover, leaf development is another important indicator of physiological status and photosynthetic potential. Coconut water at moderate to high concentrations (7.5–10%) enhanced leaf size, likely due to synergistic effects of endogenous and exogenous cytokinins promoting cell proliferation (Werner et al., 2001; Yong et al., 2009). Saba banana showed positive effects at intermediate concentrations, reflecting its natural hormone content (Islam et al., 2015; Qiao et al., 2024). In contrast, the basal medium alone produced the smallest leaves, highlighting the necessity of organic supplementation for optimal growth (Bhojwani & Razdan, 1986).

Furthermore, chlorophyll content, indicative of photosynthetic capacity, varied with organic supplementation and 6-BAP application. Higher concentrations of Saba banana sometimes reduced chlorophyll, possibly due to osmotic stress or over-proliferation under high cytokinin influence (Hamdeni et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2022; Rassol et al., 2024; Wang & Yeh, 2024). Treatments with moderate supplementation maintained higher chlorophyll, suggesting better physiological performance and potential acclimatisation success (Preece & Suther, 1991; Yang et al., 2015; Gonzales-Alvarado & Cardoso, 2024).

Additionally, water content, critical for cell turgor and metabolic activity, was highest in 2.5–5% coconut water treatments with 6-BAP, likely reflecting enhanced cellular hydration due to cytokinins, sugars, and vitamins (Yong et al., 2009; Lazim et al., 2015). In contrast, 10% coconut water

or high Saba banana concentrations reduced water loss, possibly due to denser tissue or slower metabolic activity, which can favour acclimatisation (Hura et al., 2007; Preece & Suther, 1991; Deb & Imchen, 2010; Bag et al., 2019). Optimal tissue growth appears to result from moderate supplementation balancing growth promotion and water retention (Rout et al., 2000a).

Also, stomatal characteristics provide insights into plantlet physiological status. Treatments with coconut water or Saba banana, especially combined with 6-BAP, produced larger stomatal complexes and wider apertures, suggesting enhanced gas exchange potential (Hetherington & Woodward, 2003; Pillitteri & Torii, 2012; Farber et al., 2016). Knudson C alone had the smallest stomata, underscoring the importance of organic additives for microanatomical development and balanced auxin-cytokinin interactions (Bhojwani & Razdan, 1986; Sosnowski et al., 2023).

Overall, these results indicate that fruit-derived organic supplements can partially replace exogenous hormones, enhancing morphogenesis, physiological health, and tissue quality in calamansi embryo culture. The effects are concentration-dependent, highlighting the importance of optimising supplementation levels to maximise plantlet growth and acclimatisation potential.

Conclusions

The study demonstrated that the *in vitro* growth of mature calamansi embryos was enhanced by Saba banana and mature coconut water extracts, even in the absence of synthetic hormones 6-BAP, as shown by improvements in plant height, shoot and root length, leaf traits, stomatal features, chlorophyll content, and water retention. These findings suggest that commonly discarded fruit extracts can serve as effective organic supplements and/or hormone replacement for plant tissue culture, particularly for Calamansi micropropagation. Further chemical analysis

and hormone quantification are recommended to identify the active compounds responsible for the observed growth-promoting effects. This work supports the potential of agricultural by-products in advancing sustainable plant propagation practices.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, J.C.D.; methodology, J.C.D. and M.J.G.V.; software, J.C.D.; validation, M.J.G.V., S.P.K. and R.M.R.D.; formal analysis, J.C.D.; investigation, J.C.D.; resources, J.C.D., M.J.G.V., R.M.R.D., S.P.K.; data curation, J.C.D.; writing—original draft preparation, J.C.D.; writing—review and editing, J.C.D., M.J.G.V., R.M.R.D., S.P.K.; visualization, J.C.D. and M.J.G.V.; supervision, M.J.G.V., R.M.R.D., S.P.K.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Research data is available at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19044104>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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